

Impact of Standard Operating Procedures on Accident Risk in the Transportation of Hazardous Materials: The Moderating Role of Aviation Safety and the Mediating Role of Accident Risk

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Abstract

Background: Domestic shipments of dangerous goods in Indonesia have experienced several incidents involving human factors during identification, receiving, handling, marking, and placement.

Objective: The objective of the research was to empirically demonstrate (1) the role of standard operating procedures (SOP) as a moderator of accident risk and flight safety and (2) the effect of accident risk as a mediator between professional personnel, supervision, and information technology on flight safety.

Methodology: This research employed a mixed-methods approach, utilising data derived from questionnaire copies distributed to 320 respondents across five stakeholder groups and processed using the Smart-PLS4 data analysis tool.

Results. The output path coefficient results indicate a T-statistic of 1.712 and a p-value of 0.043, demonstrating a positive role of standard operating procedures as a moderator between accident risk and flight safety. However, it is not deemed highly significant. The mediating role of accident

risk from various independent variables on flight safety is deemed positive and important, particularly concerning three variables: professional personnel, facilities and infrastructure, and supervision, evidenced by a t-statistic exceeding 1.96 and a p-value of $\alpha < 0.05$. This indicates that the impact of accident risk as a mediating variable is more significant than that of standard operating procedures as a moderating factor in this study. Information technology has a positive impact on aviation safety mediated by accident risk.

Conclusion: The risk of accidents serves as a mediator that positively impacts the influence of professional staff, facilities, infrastructure, and aviation safety oversight, albeit with a minimal structural level of influence. The moderation of SOP is asserted to enhance the impact of accident risks on aviation safety.

Unique contribution: The research contributes to the literature regarding the role of SOPs as moderator variables that determine accident risk and flight safety.

Key Recommendation: Supervision is essential for every activity in the domestic shipping of dangerous goods. SOPs must also be provided for each company to ensure their suitability and implementation for all related staff.

Keywords: Dangerous Goods; Standard Operating Procedure; Safety Flight; Risk of Accidents; Stakeholder

Introduction

All parties involved in the aviation industry, including airport operators, airline operators, air traffic controllers, aircraft maintenance operators, and other stakeholders involved in the operational process, must be fully aware of the importance of achieving flight safety, which is the primary goal that must be met in any form of transportation, but particularly in air travel (Rizaldy et al., 2023). Close to the mode of air transportation, which actively supports national development initiatives across all domains and is utilized to move people and commodities. Its benefit is that it is faster than other modes of transportation (Meixell & Norbis, 2008). The category of commodities sent by air transportation is separated into two (two) parts: general cargo and special cargo, the latter of which includes the category of dangerous items (Zhang & Zhang, 2002)

According to standard operating procedures (SOPs), handling dangerous goods requires the assistance of competent personnel and facilities that adhere to regulations. This is necessary to prevent risks and to ensure that dangerous goods are handled correctly and efficiently (Gunawan & Medianto, 2017). According to the Dangerous Items Regulation, skilled personnel must handle and package dangerous items in addition to handling them (Rechkoska et al., 2012). SOPs are software that functions to regulate certain stages and work processes. They are routine, so they are standardized into written documents, which are then used as standards (Saurin & Gonzalez, 2013). Companies, institutions, and teams create and design operational procedures through formal and well-coordinated processes to increase work productivity and minimize errors (Davison et al., 2012).

Dangerous goods are categorized into nine classifications, each requiring a distinct SOP for receiving, identifying, packaging, marking, documenting, handling, and shipping, as stipulated in the International Air Transport Association Dangerous Goods Regulation (IATA DGR) manual (Heilig & Voß, 2017). Majid et al. (2022) stated that to improve flight safety, reducing the risk of accidents is important. Stakeholders must employ experts proficient in managing hazardous

materials to ensure the identification, handling, placement, and packaging of such goods comply with relevant regulations (Mady & El-Khoury, 2023).

Several gaps in the existing research, as highlighted by Ulfa (2022), which examines the SOP that aviation security officers are required to perform for passengers and their luggage before boarding an aircraft, serve as potential sources of novelty for this research. Anggraeni and Fauziah (2022) focused on executing SOP by PT. Gapura Angkasa at Ahmad Yani Airport in Semarang. Prior research examining the function of information technology as a mediator of performance indicated that technology only predicted the impact of work experience on performance and communication skills on aviation safety performance (Harjanti et al., 2021). Windariyati and Widagdo (2022) found that the dangerous goods packaging process is carried out by professional staff with a license in the dangerous goods packaging and shipping process and must implement SOPs to prevent unwanted incidents.

In contrast to prior studies, this research focuses on the moderating function of SOP as a variable that impacts the risk of accidents on aviation safety. It involves all stakeholders in the domestic delivery of hazardous goods via air transportation routes. One such study needs is the influence of information technology ownership on disseminating information on protocols for managing hazardous materials, which contributes to aviation security by mitigating the likelihood of accidents. The main problems conducted in this study can be formulated as follows: (1) Does the standard operating procedure as a moderating variable influence the risk of aviation safety accidents? (2) Does the risk of accidents as a moderating variable influence the relationship between the availability of professional personnel, facilities and infrastructure, supervision, and information technology on aviation safety in the domestic transportation of hazardous materials in Indonesia?

Literature Review

Aviation Safety

Safe and secure air transportation can be realized when proficient aviation security people execute the current air transportation system, complemented by reliable security equipment and processes. Air transport standards can be achieved through adherence to established criteria (Marina et al., 2023). Aviation safety is interconnected with various aspects, particularly human factors, throughout preflight and inflight operations.

Professional

Professionalism is the capacity to execute work that has been mastered or evaluated conceptually, technically, or through instruction. The term 'professional' refers to labor performed by those specifically trained or educated for such tasks, receiving compensation through salary or monetary awards for their efforts (Permana et al., 2021). Professional personnel possess a profession and requisite specialized skills (Julianto & Carnarez, 2021). Infrastructure management entails overseeing the equipment, resources, and facilities utilized in an operational process to ensure its proper execution (Sohail et al., 2005). Simultaneously, warehouse operations management must efficiently organize to ensure that commodities in the storage area or warehouse are categorized by kind, size, weight, and characteristics.

Information Technology

In addition to serving as a tool that enhances interpersonal connection and communication, information technology facilitates communication among individuals, ensuring that all acquired knowledge is effectively delivered. The information technology domain encompasses methods and facilities integral to system analysis, methodology design, programming, computer software and hardware, and the internet, all unified inside a single system. Consequently, information technology is anticipated to serve as a mechanism capable of identifying various human issues in their lives (Orlikowski & Barley, 2001). Dewett and Jones (2001) identified five aspects associated with the installation of information technology systems that enhance the roles of organizations and companies: efficiency, effectiveness, communication, collaboration, and competitiveness.

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

Steen-Tveit et al. (2024) assert that SOP is a framework to guarantee the seamless execution of operational tasks inside an organization or corporation. Peinel and Rose (2013) state that SOPs are integral to organizational planning and serve as a reference for everyday operations. In the professional realm, SOPs are directives for personnel and each operational unit. Implementing the SOP will markedly enhance the efficiency of each company's work unit regarding time, work processes, and operational costs while fostering adherence, discipline, and consistency in alignment with each unit's specific interests and needs.

Air Cargo

Chika et al. (2021) reveal that air cargo is goods sent or traded to meet needs that are accompanied by documents in the form of air waybills and follow transportation procedures. Anggraeni and Fauziah (2022) stated that cargo is defined as all varieties of commodities transported through various means, including land, sea, air, or train, typically exchanged between cities or regions.

Dangerous Goods

The dangerous products are substances that pose risks to human safety and can disrupt transportation systems, necessitating appropriate laws and regulatory agencies for their movement (Floden & Woxdenius, 2021). Dangerous Goods classification is categorized into nine danger classes according to the characteristics and nature of the hazard. Hazard classes 1, 2, 4, 5, and 6 categorize risky commodities into various divisions due to their distinct characteristics and properties while remaining within the same danger properties framework. For packaging purposes, hazard classes 3, 4, 8, and some classes 9, along with divisions 5.1 and 6.1, are categorized into three packaging groups according to their level of danger.

Risk Management

Haimes (2022) says that risk encompasses multiple interpretations, including (1) risk as the probability of loss, which refers to a scenario involving an actual loss. Risk is the potential for loss of an event occurring between zero and one; risk is defined as uncertainty; it is the divergence between actual and expected outcomes; and it is the likelihood that a result deviates from expectations. The objectives of risk management within a corporation are (1) to furnish regulators with information regarding existing hazards, (2) to mitigate losses resulting from inadequately managed risks, (3) to facilitate the development and sustainability of corporate

activities, and (4) to reduce incurred expenses. Eliminate hazards to enhance effectiveness and efficiency.

Research Methodology

This research uses mixed methods, integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches. Data collection includes focus group talks and the distribution of questionnaires utilizing a Likert scale with 50 indications across seven variables. A data analysis test was conducted using the SEM (Structural Equation Model) methodology, employing Smart-PLS4 software during the outer model testing phase. The construct indicators were deemed valid if the outer loading exceeded 0.70. Additionally, reliability assessments were conducted utilizing Cronbach's alpha values exceeding 0.70 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) greater than 0.50. The subsequent phase involves evaluating the inner model by various computations, including r-squared, Q2 predictive relevance, and Goodness of Fit (GoF), with the outcomes of the Standardised Root Mean Square (SRMR) or model fit assessment. Subsequently, ascertain the influence of each hypothesis based on the outcomes of the path coefficients test, stipulating that a hypothesis is deemed influential and significant if the p-value exceeds 0.05. The t-statistic surpasses 1.96, in addition to calculating the interpretation of the upsilon (ν) mediation effect size statistical value to ascertain the extent of this variable's influence on other variables.

Results and Discussion

Validity test

Firstly, validity research assesses the degree to which indicators can accurately measure a construct. On the other hand, reliability testing is employed to evaluate the consistency of indicators in measuring the construct. The evaluation criteria for the validity test in this dissertation are based on the loading factor, which cannot be less than 0.70. The indicator is considered invalid if the loading factor value is below 0.70.

Reliability test

Reliability testing assesses the consistency of respondents' answers to question instruments that represent the dimensions of a variable, organized as a questionnaire. Reliability testing is conducted by determining the composite reliability value of the indicator block that evaluates the construct. The composite reliability value and Cronbach's alpha must exceed 0.70 for satisfactory reliability, while the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) must have a minimum threshold of $AVE > 0.50$. All variables exhibit a Cronbach's Alpha value exceeding 0.70, confirming their reliability. Table 1 presents the test results which show that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all variables exceeds 0.50 ($AVE > 0.50$), which indicates that the results for all variables are very satisfactory.

Discriminant Validity Test by Cross Loading

The findings of the discriminant validity test indicate that the latent variable has a greater magnitude on the underlying indicator or that the indicator generated by the underlying variable has a greater magnitude relative to other variables that are not underlying the indicator. Based on Table 2, it can be concluded that all question items in the questionnaire are genuine.

Table 1: Reliability Test

Construct	<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	<i>Composite reliability (rho_a)</i>	<i>Composite reliability (rho_c)</i>	<i>Average Variance Extracted (AVE)</i>	Conclusion
Professional personnel (X1)	0,943	0,956	0,957	0,789	Reliable
Facilities and Infrastructure (X2)	0,945	0,954	0,953	0,673	Reliable
Supervision (monitoring) (X3)	0,934	0,942	0,945	0,657	Reliable
Information Technology (X4)	0,913	0,924	0,928	0,592	Reliable
Standard Operating Procedures (Z)	0,924	0,941	0,94	0,665	Reliable
Accident Risk (Y1)	0,886	0,918	0,924	0,755	Reliable
Aviation Safety (Y2)	0,847	0,848	0,897	0,686	Reliable

Table 2: Discriminant Validity Test by Cross Loading

	(X2)	(Y2)	(X3)	(X1)	(Y1)	(Z)	(X4)	(Y1)	(Y1)	(Y1)	(Y1)	(Y1)
X11	0,83	0,812	0,819	0,863	0,814	0,808	0,789	-0,63	-0,58	-0,67	-0,66	-0,56
X12	0,734	0,785	0,791	0,961	0,808	0,892	0,785	-0,53	-0,45	-0,48	-0,47	-0,4
X13	0,719	0,77	0,786	0,973	0,775	0,893	0,779	-0,47	-0,37	-0,42	-0,4	-0,32
X15	0,678	0,742	0,73	0,918	0,701	0,853	0,745	-0,46	-0,37	-0,41	-0,4	-0,32
X16	0,745	0,778	0,816	0,964	0,786	0,914	0,79	-0,47	-0,38	-0,42	-0,4	-0,32
X21	0,928	0,792	0,874	0,741	0,886	0,811	0,782	-0,69	-0,68	-0,71	-0,67	-0,58
X22	0,77	0,494	0,665	0,41	0,574	0,465	0,576	-0,36	-0,4	-0,62	-0,51	-0,45
X23	0,817	0,569	0,712	0,511	0,662	0,568	0,618	-0,42	-0,48	-0,64	-0,56	-0,42
X24	0,852	0,8	0,811	0,746	0,843	0,82	0,766	-0,64	-0,58	-0,58	-0,53	-0,49
X25	0,748	0,619	0,739	0,725	0,651	0,691	0,709	-0,33	-0,25	-0,4	-0,31	-0,29
X26	0,944	0,827	0,905	0,753	0,909	0,826	0,81	-0,66	-0,65	-0,7	-0,67	-0,58
X27	0,817	0,653	0,771	0,598	0,655	0,615	0,771	-0,47	-0,49	-0,65	-0,63	-0,56
X28	0,807	0,686	0,763	0,592	0,686	0,634	0,745	-0,48	-0,5	-0,58	-0,59	-0,5
X29	0,814	0,73	0,794	0,793	0,812	0,816	0,787	-0,62	-0,58	-0,6	-0,55	-0,57
X31	0,909	0,836	0,928	0,832	0,895	0,872	0,822	-0,62	-0,58	-0,61	-0,56	-0,5
X32	0,8	0,779	0,868	0,842	0,792	0,831	0,756	-0,52	-0,49	-0,53	-0,54	-0,43
X33	0,653	0,569	0,719	0,56	0,598	0,573	0,621	-0,29	-0,3	-0,34	-0,33	-0,29
X34	0,763	0,713	0,851	0,776	0,729	0,753	0,724	-0,37	-0,35	-0,44	-0,41	-0,29
X35	0,669	0,709	0,77	0,795	0,672	0,771	0,704	-0,37	-0,3	-0,32	-0,35	-0,23
X36	0,844	0,719	0,876	0,647	0,827	0,723	0,725	-0,55	-0,54	-0,59	-0,54	-0,48
X37	0,688	0,527	0,713	0,425	0,544	0,481	0,661	-0,35	-0,4	-0,52	-0,49	-0,44
X38	0,749	0,648	0,771	0,515	0,671	0,585	0,708	-0,38	-0,41	-0,49	-0,48	-0,41

X39	0,76	0,652	0,771	0,669	0,779	0,743	0,741	-0,52	-0,5	-0,5	-0,44	-0,48
X41	0,51	0,534	0,549	0,521	0,434	0,492	0,755	-0,2	-0,15	-0,25	-0,2	-0,19
X42	0,76	0,607	0,743	0,513	0,629	0,543	0,742	-0,39	-0,41	-0,58	-0,56	-0,47
X43	0,663	0,618	0,621	0,463	0,558	0,527	0,709	-0,41	-0,47	-0,53	-0,54	-0,41
X44	0,765	0,7	0,724	0,672	0,748	0,735	0,801	-0,5	-0,49	-0,5	-0,45	-0,42
X45	0,608	0,628	0,647	0,632	0,549	0,61	0,839	-0,2	-0,15	-0,27	-0,22	-0,2
X46	0,756	0,717	0,728	0,713	0,759	0,779	0,808	-0,56	-0,55	-0,55	-0,51	-0,48
X47	0,633	0,624	0,674	0,675	0,567	0,632	0,82	-0,23	-0,16	-0,28	-0,23	-0,26
X49	0,777	0,833	0,842	0,935	0,842	0,931	0,838	-0,5	-0,44	-0,47	-0,44	-0,36
Y11	0,937	0,823	0,925	0,814	0,927	0,852	0,842	-0,61	-0,61	-0,69	-0,65	-0,57
Y12	0,826	0,856	0,831	0,8	0,96	0,906	0,769	-0,72	-0,67	-0,58	-0,56	-0,53
Y13	0,789	0,853	0,795	0,739	0,945	0,877	0,728	-0,76	-0,69	-0,57	-0,57	-0,53

Variabel Determination by R-square

Based on the R-Square value, also known as the coefficient of determination, a variable determination test is conducted to assess how much the independent (exogenous) variable affects the dependent (endogenous) variable. The R-square value is constrained to a range of 0 to 1 and is considered optimal if the test result exceeds 0.05. The modified R-square value addresses issues observed with the R-square and is commonly employed in inferential research.

Table 3: Variable Determination by R-square

	<i>R-square</i>	<i>R-square adjusted</i>
Accident Risk (Y1)	0,858	0,856
Aviation Safety (Y2)	0,877	0,873

Table 3 shows that the R-square value for all exogenous variables impacting accident risk is 0.858. The correlation coefficient (R-square) for all external variables contributing to flight safety is 0.877. Accordingly, the R-square value rises from 0.858 to 0.877, totaling 0.019. This indicates that the determination remains optimistic, suggesting that there is still a direct and indirect influence of ownership of all exogenous variables through shared accident risk mediation.

Inner Model

Q² predictive relevance

In addition to the high R-square value, the evaluation includes Q² predictive relevance. This metric serves to verify the model's predictive capability. A model is deemed predictive if Q² is greater than 0, while it lacks predictive relevance if Q² is less than 0.

Table 4: Q² Predictive Relevance

	<i>Q²predict</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>
Accident Risk (Y1)	0,867	0,366	0,268
Aviation Safety (Y2)	0,833	0,411	0,301

Table 4 shows that the Q² value of the Y1 variable Accident risk is 0.867, which means less than zero (Q² > 0). Therefore, this variable is deemed to have predictive significance. Furthermore, the

Y2 variable Aviation Safety has a Q^2 value of 0.833 ($Q^2 > 0$), indicating a high level of predictive relevance.

Standardized Root Mean square Residual (SRMR)

Subsequently, the SRMR (Standardize Root Mean Square Residual) value is tested to assess the appropriateness of the model (model fit). If the SRMR (Standardize Root Mean Square Residual) is less than 0.08, it indicates model suitability. Conversely, if it exceeds 0.08, it does not indicate model suitability (fit model). Values ranging from 0.08 to 1.00 still indicate acceptable data.

Table 5: Standardized Root Mean square Residual (SRMR)

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0,105	0,105
d_ ULS	10,818	10,889
d_ G	13,196	13,368
Chi-square	13343,828	13468,549
NFI	0,521	0,517

Table 5 shows that the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value is 0.105, higher than 0.08. This indicates a lack of model fit. However, the model is still considered suitable for use and will be continued in the following research process since the results are below 1.00.

Output Path Coefficients

Table 6: Output Path Coefficients Moderating Variable

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	95% Confidence Interval		T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
				5%	95%		
Standard Operating Procedures x Accident Risk -> Aviation Safety	-0,069	-0,07	0,04	-0,131	0	1,712	0,043
Professional Personel (X1) -> Accident Risk (Y1) -> Aviation Safety (Y2)	0,09	0,086	0,03	0,036	0,138	3,013	0,001

Facilities and Infrastructure -> Accident Risk > Aviation Safety	0,167	0,161	0,053	0,063	0,246	3,145	0,001
Supervision (monitoring) -> Accident Risk > aviation safety	0,094	0,091	0,033	0,039	0,147	2,83	0,002
H7 : Information Technology -> Accident Risk > aviation safety	-0,027	-0,027	0,019	-0,059	0	1,412	0,079

Table 6 presents the test of the impact of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) in moderating the relationship between accident risk and flight safety. The test results found that with a p-value of 0.043 and a t-statistic of 1.712, indicating a positive and significant role of SOP in mitigating accident risk on flight safety-

The calculated particular indirect effects, namely the personal-professional relationship mediated by accident risk on aviation safety, can be elucidated by the probability value (p-value) of 0.003 and the degree of significance derived from the t-statistic value of 2.781. These two findings indicate a substantial correlation between personal professionals and flight safety, which is influenced by the likelihood of accidents via mediation. Therefore, Hypothesis 12 is confirmed. The correlation between facilities and infrastructure, influenced by accident risk and aviation safety, may be elucidated by the probability value (p-value) of 0.002 and the critical significance level derived from the T-statistic value of 2.941. These two findings indicate a substantial correlation between the presence of facilities and infrastructure, which is indirectly influenced by the risk of accidents, and the safety of flights. Hypothesis 13 has been confirmed.

The specific indirect impact test results concerning the monitoring link mediated by accident risk on aviation safety can be elucidated by the probability value (p-value) of 0.004 and the degree of significance derived from the T-statistic value of 2.622. These findings indicate a correlation between supervision (monitoring) and flight safety, which is influenced by the risk of accidents.

An analysis of the impact and correlation between information technology and accident risk on aviation safety reveals a p-value of 0.096 and a T-statistic value of 1.302, indicating a significant association. The current hypothesis employs a significance level of $\epsilon = 10\%$ or ($P < 0.1$). Thus, these two findings suggest that the accessibility of information technology has a negligible impact on the mediated risk of accidents concerning aviation safety.

Conclusion

The results of the Structural Equation Model (SEM) test indicate that out of the 15 hypotheses, 12 hypotheses demonstrate positive correlations. These hypotheses include facilities, infrastructure, professional personnel, supervision (monitoring), and information technology. The significance values for these relationships vary, namely $\epsilon = 10\%$. However, this influence is not statistically significant. Meanwhile, information technology and Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) influence aviation safety considerably. In addition to operating as a mediating variable, the

probability of accidents also positively and substantially impacts flight safety. In addition, implementing Standard Operating Procedures (SOP), enhancing facilities and infrastructure, and implementing supervision (monitoring) to mitigate the risk of accidents have a beneficial and substantial impact on aviation safety.

Conflict of interest

The authors hereby declare that no conflict of interest exists

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